

1 **Title:** Quantification of the biocontrol agent *Trichoderma harzianum* with real-time
2 TaqMan PCR and its potential extrapolation to the hyphal biomass.

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18 **Abstract:**

19 The species of the genus *Trichoderma* are used successfully as biocontrol agents against
20 a wide range of phytopathogenic fungi. Among them, the specie *Trichoderma harzianum*
21 is especially effective. However, the use of biocontrol fungi in soil is in need of tools for
22 monitorization, in order to provide accurate measurements and management of the
23 environment. In this context, the molecular biology techniques and the real-time PCR in
24 particular, are becoming important and effective tool for the quantification of fungi in
25 sample. The aim of this study consisted of the development and application of a real-time

1 PCR-based method to the quantification of *T. harzianum*, and the extrapolation of these
2 data to fungal biomass values. A set of primers and a TaqMan probe were designed and
3 tested, based in the ITS region of the fungal genome; amplification was correlated to
4 biomass measurements obtained with optical microscopy and image analysis, of the
5 hyphal length of the mycelium of the colony. A correlation of 0.76 between ITS copies
6 and biomass was obtained. The extrapolation of the quantity of ITS copies, calculated
7 with real-time PCR, into quantities of fungal biomass will provide a more real, useful and
8 practical value of the quantity of soil fungi.

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10

11 **Keywords:** hyphal biomass; ITS copies; Real-time PCR; TaqMan Probe; *Trichoderma*
12 *harzianum*

13

14 **1. Introduction**

15 Fungal species of the genus *Trichoderma* (e.g. *Trichoderma harzianum*) have been used
16 as biological control agents in agriculture for many years (Papavizas, 1985; Chet, 1987).
17 These antagonistic fungi act as mycoparasites of phytopathogenic fungi, secreting
18 hydrolytic enzymes and antibiotic compounds (Howell, 2003), competing for space and
19 nutrients with other microorganisms (Hjeljord & Tronsmo, 1998), stimulating plant
20 growth and induce acquired resistance mechanism in the presence of biotic and abiotic
21 stress (Bailey and Lumsden, 1998).

22 One of the most important aspects of the use of this biological control agent is the
23 application of tools which permit its monitoring (quantification) in soils and organic
24 substrates (compost). The use of real-time PCR together with fluorescent-tagged markers
25 has allowed the quantification of numerous species of mycorrhizal fungi,

1 phytopathogens and biological control agents. In contrast to classical techniques such as
2 plate counting (Atkins et al., 2005) and biomass measures of fungal components (e.g.
3 chitin, ergosterol or fatty acids) (Ekblad et al., 1997; Olsson et al., 2003) or monoclonal
4 antibody technology (Thornton, 2008), the real-time PCR technique is faster and has
5 higher sensitivity. Its hands-free post-PCR capacity avoids possible contamination
6 (Scheda et al., 2004).

7 The aim of this work was to extrapolate the amount of DNA quantified by real-time
8 TaqMan PCR into fungal biomass calculated from microscopic measurements of hyphal
9 length and image analysis (Raidl et al., 2005).

10

11 **2. Methods**

12 *2.1. Fungal strains and growth conditions*

13 The experiments were carried out with the isolate *T. harzianum* T-78 (CECT 20714,
14 Spanish Type Culture Collection) selected from green compost. The other isolates were
15 obtained from CECT (Table 1). The isolates were grown in potato dextrose agar (PDA)
16 at 26 °C in darkness for 7 days, and stored at 4° C on PDA slant tubes; and in potato
17 dextrose broth (PDB) at 26 °C in darkness, at 150 rpm, for 48 hours.

18

19 *2.2. DNA extraction*

20 Two millilitres of each PDB culture were centrifuged at 18000g; the mycelium was
21 washed with 1.5 ml of TE buffer (10 mM TrisHCl, 1 mM EDTA) and centrifuged again.
22 Five-hundred µl of re-suspension buffer (50 mM TrisHCl, 10 mM EDTA, 1% SDS, pH
23 7.5) was shaken with glass beads (425-600 µm) (Sigma-Aldrich Inc., USA) in an
24 oscillating mill (MM400, Retsch, Germany). One hundred and fifty µl of potassium
25 acetate solution (3 M, pH 4.8) were added to the supernatant and the mixture centrifuged

1 at 18000g. The supernatant was collected and 600 µl of isopropanol were added for
2 nucleic acid precipitation, followed by centrifugation at 18000g for 20 min at 4 °C. The
3 precipitate was washed with ice-cold 70 % ethanol, centrifuged, dried at room
4 temperature, re-suspended in 50 µl of water (AccuGENE, Cambrex, USA) and treated
5 with RNase (20 mg/L) for 20 min at 37 °C.

6

7 *2.3. Specific primers and probe design*

8 The ITS region of the ribosomal DNA of *T. harzianum* was amplified (Takara PCR
9 Thermal Cycler Dice TM, Takara Bio Inc., Japan), sequenced (White et al. 1990), and the
10 sequences were compared with sequences available in the NCBI database for other
11 *Trichoderma* species. Different sets of primers and a TaqMan probe (Table 1) were
12 designed inside this region and analyzed for specificity using the NCBI Blast feature
13 (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/BLAST>). Different combinations of these primers were
14 tested against different isolates of the genus *Trichoderma* (Table 1).

15

16 *2.4. Real-time PCR conditions*

17 Real-time PCR amplifications were performed in a total volume of 8 µl using a
18 LightCyclerTM (Roche Diagnostics, Germany). The reaction mixtures contained a final
19 concentration of 0.3 µM each primer, 0.025 µM TaqMan probe, 4 µl *Premix Ex Taq*TM
20 (Takara Bio Inc., Japan), 0.8 µl template DNA and 1.84 µl sterile water (AccuGENE
21 Cambrex, USA). The thermal cycling conditions for amplification were an initial
22 denaturation at 95 °C for 35 sec, followed by 35 cycles each consisting of a denaturation
23 step at 95 °C for 5 sec, annealing at 64 °C for 15 sec, and extension at 72 °C for 15 sec.
24 The amplification results were analysed with LightCyclerTM Software 4 (Roche Applied
25 Science, Switzerland).

1

2 *2.5. Development of a standard curve*

3 A fragment of 621-bp from the selected ITS region of the *T. harzianum* T-78, was cloned
4 in to vector pCR 2.1 (Invitrogen, USA). The plasmid was used to transform *E. coli* DH5 α
5 cells (Invitrogen, USA) and purified with a QIAprep Miniprep Kit (Qiagen, Germany);
6 the presence of inserts was determined by RFLP (Restriction Fragment Length
7 Polymorphism) using four restriction enzymes: *TaqI*, *EcoRI*, *HinfI* and *AluI* (Fermentas,
8 USA). The DNA concentration of the plasmid standard solution was measured
9 spectroscopically (NanoDrop ND-1000, Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc., USA) and was
10 related to the known molecular weight of a single plasmid molecule. The concentration
11 was adjusted to the number of 10¹¹ ITS copies, and the standard was diluted in 10-fold
12 steps to obtain the standard curve.

13

14 *2.6. Hyphal biomass measurement*

15 Hyphal biomass was estimated according to Raidl et al. (2005), with some modifications:
16 *T. harzianum* mycelium was grown in slides covered with Hagem's Agar (Stenlid, 1985),
17 and kept in humid chambers at room temperature for 72 hours. Slides with appropriate
18 hyphal growth (homogeneous and not too dense) were selected, covered with a cover slip
19 with a grid pattern on the surface (Raidl et al., 2005) and photographed with a digital
20 camera (Kappa DX 20L, Kappa opto-electronics, Gleichen, Germany) through a Dialux
21 22 microscope (Leitz, Wetzlar, Germany) at a magnification of 63x. The pictures were
22 processed with Adobe Photoshop 8.0 (Adobe Systems Inc., USA) in order to enhance the
23 contrast of the hyphae against the background in the pictures. The hyphal length of the
24 whole slide was measured with the WinRhizo software 4.0b (Regent Instruments Inc.,
25 Quebec, Canada) and was changed to hyphal volume using the cylinder equation ($V = L$

1 * $\pi * r^2$; L: hyphal length; r: hyphal radius), assuming that the hyphae of *Trichoderma* are
2 perfectly cylindrical and using an average value of the hyphal diameter (calculated taking
3 into account the percentages of thin and thick branches). This volume was converted to
4 fungal dry weight using the conversion factors (f: specific weight for fungal hyphae: 0.22
5 g cm⁻³) (Fogel & Hunt, 1978) obtained from the literature (Raidl et al. 2005).

6

7 2.7. Quantification of ITS copy numbers

8 Immediately after the pictures were taken, the mycelia grown on the slide was collected
9 carefully for DNA extraction (FastDNA SPIN Kit for Soil, Q-BIOgene, USA), following
10 the manufacturer's instructions with some modifications: i) the samples were
11 homogenized in an oscillating mill for 1 hour, to ensure total cell lysis, ii) the SPINTM
12 Filter was eluted up to 4 times with a greater volume of sterile water to ensure that all
13 DNA was collected. The number of ITS copies of each elution was calculated using the
14 LightCyclerTM System as described above, using five replicates of undiluted, 1/10 and
15 1/100 diluted DNA template. An external standard and a negative control (water) were
16 run in every real-time PCR reaction. The amount of detected ITS copies was calculated
17 with the Roche Software by interpolating the cycle threshold with the standard curve, and
18 extrapolating to the total sample volume.

19

20 3. Results and discussion

21 3.1 Specificity of the primers and probe

22 Currently, the ribosomal RNA gene cluster provides the main region for molecular studies
23 with fungi, such as detection, quantification and phylogenetic studies of different taxa
24 (Bridge and Spooner, 2001; Lievens et al., 2006). The different primers designed inside
25 ITS1 and ITS2 regions only showed significant matches with *T. harzianum* sequences

1 (BLAST). The set of primers ITS1 S/ ITS1 R, which amplified a 211-bp fragment,
2 together with the fluorescent probe ITS1 TM Fam, amplified all the *T. harzianum* isolates
3 used in this study (Table 1). The design of primers in the ITS1 region allows the detection
4 of low quantities of target DNA, due to the presence of multiple different copies of rRNA
5 spacer regions in the fungus genome, increasing the specificity of the real-time PCR
6 (Bridge and Spooner, 2001).

7 The development of this primers and probe allows the detection of *T. harzianum* in pure
8 cultures and therefore, in the future, could be used for detection and quantification in soils
9 and organic substrates.

10

11 *3.2 Calibration of real-time PCR*

12 Serial dilutions of the plasmid over 10 orders of magnitude were carried out to obtain a
13 standard curve for the real-time PCR calibration, starting with an initial concentration of
14 247.12 ng DNA/ μl , which was calculated as representing 1×10^{11} ITS copies/ μl . A
15 standard curve ranging over six orders of magnitude (from 10^7 to 10^2 ITS copies/ μl) was
16 achieved by plotting the cycle thresholds against the logarithm of the initial number of
17 target copies, with an efficiency of 2,037. The external standard used routinely for
18 quantification in sample materials was 10^5 ITS copies/ μl . The number of specific ITS
19 gene copies potentially give a more real measure of the amount of the microorganism
20 present in the sample (Savazzini et al., 2008), versus other studies that use standard curves
21 based on ten-fold serial dilutions of DNA for the calibration of the real-time PCR, and
22 expressing the results as quantity of DNA (Filion et al., 2003; Lievens et al., 2006).

23

24 *3.3 Extrapolation curve for the number of ITS copies vs. biomass measurements*

1 One of the main aspects of this work was the conversion of the number of copies of a
2 specific gene into fungal biomass, making possible the extrapolation of the obtained data
3 to a more realistic and easily understandable unit such as biomass.

4 Seven slides were appropriate (hyphal growth was homogenous and not too dense) for
5 this extrapolation. The mycelia were grown on different, independent slides. After three
6 days, the total lengths of the mycelia were measured and converted into fungal dry
7 biomass. The average hyphal radius was also measured in the slides accounting for the
8 different hyphal thickness. The hyphal thickness was classified in thick and thin hyphae
9 (higher or lower than 4-4.5 μm); the percentage of both types of hyphae in the culture
10 was calculated and was 37.9% for thinner hyphae and 62.1% for thicker hyphae. The
11 hyphal length, volume, and biomass results, with the number of ITS copies present on
12 each slide are shown in Table 2. Combining these two methods, a mean of $2.67 \cdot 10^4$ ITS
13 copies per mm of hypha was derived. The correlation of the two sets of data by linear
14 regression analysis gave an R^2 value of 0.7575 (Figure 1), for the equation: $y = 1.48 \cdot 10^{-5}$
15 $x + 1047.28$. This standard curve permits the extrapolation to *T. harzianum* biomass
16 through a specific probe. It could be stated that the obtained value was not so high, but
17 this may be correlated to the mycelium age, in spite of the fact that slides were processed
18 in the same way during the three-day inoculation. The selection of the area to photograph
19 also influenced this correlation, related to the type fungal growth. During the colony
20 development, the hyphae are stretching, branching and fusing, and show different
21 morphological features along the mycelium (Buller, 1933). All these changes involve
22 cytoplasmatic and nuclear movements through the mycelium. These movements are well
23 documented in other ascomycetes species like *Gelasinospora tetrasperma*, *Blastomyces*
24 *dermatitis* (Dowding & Bakerspiegel, 1954), and *Aspergillus nidulans* (Suelmann &
25 Fischer, 2000). These phenomena can influence the nuclear distribution in the older

1 hyphae in comparison to younger hyphae of the mycelium, and consequently the
2 correlation.

3 The average radius value used in this work was based on measurements of the colonies,
4 accounting for the percentage and abundance of thicker and thinner hyphae. This relation
5 could vary depending on the culture medium or mycelium age, influencing the biomass
6 data, and ultimately the ITS/biomass correlation.

7 Moreover, the number of slides analyzed would also be related to the correlation obtained,
8 due to the analysis time that each one entails (Raidl et al., 2005).

9

10 **5. Conclusions**

11 The application of real-time PCR using a specifically-designed probe has been
12 demonstrated to be an effective tool for the quantification of *T. harzianum* in pure
13 cultures; moreover its extrapolation to biomass measures, like fungal dry weight in this
14 study, would allow a more practical knowledge of the quantity of fungus. The potential
15 use of this technique in soil and compost would be very useful, improving the application
16 of the fungus in field, and thus improving the results in their employment against
17 phytopathogenic fungi; although future experiments would be necessary to improve and
18 optimize this technique in soil or compost samples, more complex than pure cultures.

19

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